

Sustainability Reporting and Financial Performance of Listed Financial Institutions in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: This study investigated the impact of sustainability reporting on financial institutions' financial performance in Nigeria. The fifty-two listed financial institutions on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, from 2010 to 2020 form the population of the study. A judgmental sampling basis was used to select 30 listed firms. This study used a longitudinal study approach as well as an ex-post facto research design to meet the study's objectives. Data analysis approaches include content analysis of the sustainability reporting index indicators provided in Global Reporting Initiative Guidelines G4 (GRIG4) and multiple regressions. Proxies for corporate sustainability are reports on economic, environmental, and social activities. Financial performance is proxies by returns on assets. Secondary data used was extracted from the firm's annual reports. With a beta coefficient of -0.053, a t statistic of the value of -3.099, and a significance value of 0.002, the result shows that Economic activity reporting and Financial Performance are related. With a beta coefficient of 0.093, a t statistic value of 2.931, and a significance value of 0.004, the result shows that social activity reporting and Financial Performance are related. Also, with a beta coefficient of 0.035, a t statistic value of 1.368, and a significance value of 0.172, the result shows that environmental activity reporting and Financial Performance are related but not significant. This study concluded that sustainability reporting impacts financial institutions' financial performance in Nigeria.

Key words: Sustainability, Environment, Social, Economic, legitimacy, stakeholder.

Introduction

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

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Discussion

1. Introduction

The phrase "sustainability reporting" (SR) is frequently employed to showcase a business's influence on the performance of its social, environmental, and economic aspects. In order to satisfy the needs of a wide range of stakeholders, including governments, activist groups, workers, creditors, investors, customers, suppliers, and the general public, these reports are distributed and published. Recently, it has been used to disclose a company's commitment to adopting socially and environmentally friendly practices. SR has grown in importance as a tool for businesses and organizations to address the growing need for transparency from consumers, investors, other stakeholders, and society as a whole. There has been an increase in sustainability reports from the continent of Africa due to the region's growing interest in sustainability practices and the pressure on businesses to be environmentally friendly. Organisations make use of sustainability reports to relate voluntary information on their environmental, economic and social activities to the impact the public. The information aids businesses in closing information gaps and increasing transparency about their sustainability performance, whether good or bad. Higher openness, on the other hand, allows investors to make more accurate assessments and better direct their investments towards the companies that have greater impacts. This thereby translates to higher competitive advantage for the organisations that demonstrate their social commitments, accountability, and sustainability in conduct by earning the legitimacy and societal approval they require and market advantages. As a result, businesses are increasingly concentrating on sustainability programs and developing more sustainable business models, as well as implementing new reporting systems. Incorporating the concept of social responsibility into sustainability reports demonstrates long-term ethical belief. Sustainability reports are a set of social duties that apply to every report that includes information about the environment, society, and economy.

Financial performance is a measure of a company's ability to generate revenue from its assets. It's an extensive evaluation of a firm's global financial health over a period of time (Kenton 2021). However, relying solely on financial data to appraise a company's performance is insufficient. Sustainability reports are a type of report that contains non-financial information on firm's social, environmental and economic performance. They are one technique for improving financial performance in line with the Global Reporting Initiative. Sustainability reports are optional disclosures of information about a company's economic, environmental, and social implications on the organization's and host community's long-term growth (Epstein, 2008). This enables businesses to close information gaps and boost transparency about their favorable and unfavorable environmental performance. However, sustainability reporting is not widely used in Nigeria; just a few enterprises, particularly in the industrial sector, publish sustainability reports. Due to the need for information and the level of required corporate transparency currently in place, a number of groups have developed (voluntary) reporting standards for ESG operations, with the purpose of improving or unifying reporting approaches. The

Sustainability Accounting Standard Board, for example, designs "industry-specific reporting requirements straddling financially essential environmental, social, and control areas" that companies can utilize in their Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) disclosures, likewise, the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) creates global SR standards to assist firms in "communicating their contribution on major sustainability concerns. The IFRS Foundation is the most recent arrival, aiming to overcome the multiplicity of standards and standard setters by providing a global approach to sustainability reporting. The GRI has helped companies all around the world adopt the practice of sustainability reporting as a pioneer in the field. In a sustainability report, an organization's goals, culture, and dedication to fostering a sustainable global economy are outlined, regardless of the repercussions. Non-financial problems, such as the social and environmental characteristics, are increasingly being reported on around the world as a result of a growing trend among corporations to report non-financial crises. According to GRI, "businesses and organizations adhered to publish reports about the environmental, economic and social impacts generated by their everyday actions". Minuscule research has explored the impact of sustainability reporting on performance of financial institutions in Nigeria, Companies are obligated to provide a report that includes their social, economic, and environmental repercussions, in addition to standard financial statements that focus on profit and financial status, under the notion of sustainability. It is envisaged that such a practice will encourage businesses to pay more attention to the environmental impact of their activities, because a growing number of investors are interested in methods that take gives significance importance to social, environmental, and economic factors, also known as sustainable investment. As a result, this research aims to investigate the impact of sustainability reporting on financial institution performance in Nigeria, by examining the impact of economic, environmental, and social reporting on the performance of listed financial institutions in Nigeria, using ROA as key performance indicators in line with previous studies. This study would add to the body of knowledge regarding sustainability reporting in Nigeria

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Financial performance

Financial performance is a depiction of a business's protracted financial strength, as assessed by Capital adequacy, solvency, and profitability metrics, in terms of fundraising and fund distribution. The investigation of a company's financial ratios can reveal its financial performance, and Profitability is one metric used to assess financial performance. Firm performance is an economic metric that evaluates a business's competency to accomplish its goals by combining human and material resources (Le, 2015). Profitability is the most crucial factor in the business world of today. The return on assets (ROA) statistic evaluates a company's profitability to its total assets. This ratio evaluates a company's performance by contrasting its profit (net income) to the money (capital) it has committed to investing in assets. The bigger the return, the more efficient and productive management is when using economic resources (assets). In terms of ROA, organizations with a greater number of assets should be able to earn more money (Otekurin, Nwanji, Olowookere, Egbide, Fakile, Lawal, and Eluyela, 2018). The amount of income used in this calculation is income before taxes and interest costs. Since interest is the payment made to creditors in

exchange for the resources they lend the business. This study adopts ROA as a proxy for financial Performance.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical underpinnings of this study include legitimacy theory, stakeholder theory, Signaling theory, and theory of sustainability.

Legitimacy Theory

Dowling & Pfeffer, (1975) propounded Legitimacy theory (LT), and LT prompted an intuition of Institution and social system theory, which considers organizations to be complex components that must interact with their environments to survive (Cuganesan, Ward, & Guthrie, 2007). LT states that a firm must continue to integrate its values with those of the social system it operates to achieve legitimate status, which is the acceptance and support of society as well as the removal of threats to its existence (Cuganesan, Ward, & Guthrie, 2007; Noah, 2017). The theory of legitimacy offers a contrivance for understanding social and environmental disclosures made by companies. LT aids in comprehending how the company behaves when creating, executing, and promoting its social responsibility strategies (Zyznarska-Dworczak, 2018). According to the legitimacy theory, businesses provide information about their social responsibility to portray a socially responsible image and so justify their actions and defend their existence to their stakeholder groups. The notion that business and society have a social contract forms the basis of LT. It is a theory that presupposes firms are making an effort to make sure the activities they do comply with accepted social laws and norms (Andriof, Waddock, Husted, & Rahman, 2017). For the business to be recognized by society, it uses a sustainability report to convey its sense of responsibility to the economy, society, and environment to be accepted by the society as businesses gain the support of society, they are expected to perform better and generate higher profits. This research is supported by the presence of stakeholder theory in conjunction with the legitimacy theory.

Stakeholder Theory

Dr. F. Edward Freeman introduced the stakeholder theory in 1984 with the idea that a firm's true success is in pleasing all of its stakeholders, not just those who stand to gain financially from its stock (Owolabi, Owolabi, Otekunrin, & Kwarbia, 2023). Those who advocate stakeholder theory do so from a managerial standpoint. In addition to requiring efficient corporate monitoring, managerial credibility, and reduced agency costs—all of which raise equity—it also assumes that management may decide to make sustainability reports available to the public as a motivator. The majority of stakeholders share an objective in common, but this does not mean that agency costs cannot occur. By acting against the best interests of the community, stakeholders drive up agency costs. In addition, when people become more interested in the environment, there is more interest in SR (Asogwa 2016). According to stakeholder theory, stakeholders have a right to information, including details about the business's operations and the operating environment, especially as it relates to how the operations impact or impact them. It comprises a company's social actions as well as its societal responsibilities. Stakeholder theory touches on both societal and stakeholder accountability. The individual acquires the legal right to demand that firms

report on the social impact of their activity. By enforcing accountability accounting, stakeholder theory creates a form of social contract between society and business. It usually emphasizes how business and the operational environment are intertwined (Owolabi, Owolabi, Otekunrin, & Kwarbia, 2023).. The problem lies in the fact that management determines the extent of stakeholder engagement by withholding information from their privy that they deem necessary—basically, information required to enhance the company's reputation—instead of revealing what is genuinely transparent and accountable. The management is in complete control of the procedure and puts the firm's interests ahead of society's, evaluating how business affects society rather than how society affects business. Stakeholder theory holds that a company cannot exist solely to benefit its shareholders; it must also benefit other stakeholders. The corporation exposes both financial and non-financial information in its sustainability report, allowing enterprises to communicate more clearly with the public about the non-financial management and performance aspects of their businesses. A firm must deliver benefits to its stakeholders in addition to operating for its advantage. As a result, the company's image will be enhanced and probably its financial performance will be enhanced too. It is for these this study adopts stakeholder theory.

Signaling theory

Signaling theory was propounded based on observed knowledge gaps between organizations and prospective employees by Michael Spence (1973). The notion of signaling can be used to explain behaviour when two parties (individuals and institutions) have varying degrees of information. Typically, the decision to convey (or signal) such information rests with the sender, and the receiver must determine how to decipher the signal (Connelly, Certo, Ireland, & Reutzel, 2011). Signaling theory is significant because it minimizes information asymmetry; however, to do so, it is necessary to understand the perspectives and perceptions of the players involved in the process, in this case, employees, to remove distortion (Carter, 2006; Connelly et al., 2011). As a result, signaling theory is widely discussed in management literature such as strategic management, entrepreneurship, and human resource management (Connelly, Certo, Ireland, & Reutzel, 2011). Signaling theory seeks to lessen the informational imbalance between two parties (Spence, 2002). Firms use sustainability reporting to send signals to stakeholders and for this reason, Signaling theory adopted in this study.

Theory of Sustainability

One interpretation of the theory of sustainability is that it takes into account how businesses must exist both now and in the future (Tran and Beddewela, 2020). In light of this concept of uncertainty, the business exists and engages the environment not only to pursue profit but also because it feels compelled to support social welfare and the communities in which it exists (Camodeca et al., 2018). This idea is sometimes described as the 3Ps (Profit i.e. Economics, People i.e. social welfare, and Planet i.e. the environment) or the Triple Bottom Line idea. According to Hsiao et al. (2022), sustainability reporting is the process of capturing and disseminating accounting data that demonstrates a company's performance in both financial and non-financial areas, such as social, environmental, and economic aspects. The fields of social and environmental accounting frequently diverge

from sustainability accounting (Tilt, 2018). The topic of social accounting centres on how to document in accounting the social implications, social advantages, and the degree to which businesses support the social facets of a community. Environmental accounting addresses the methods used for capturing environmental advantages and drawbacks in both quantitative and qualitative terms in corporate reporting. Sustainability reporting is defined as "a report published by a firm or organization about social, environmental, and economic impacts" by Rahman and Alsayegh (2021). The environmental elements encompass the degree to which the company's activities affect the environment as well as the steps taken by the company to mitigate its adverse consequences and practice sustainable development. The social dimension pertains to the degree to which the firm's activities consider social and cultural matters within the community, encompassing the integration of inclusivity within the firm's commercial activities. Lastly, the degree to which the firm's governance structures and practices facilitate the execution of strategic plans and managerial oversight of economic activities that promote the firm's sustainability is the governance component. Social performance theory—which draws heavily from theories of legitimacy and stakeholder relations—is the source of sustainability theory. According to stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory, businesses should consider their stakeholders' interests and demonstrate that they are in operation to serve their varied constituencies, which may consist of the desires of the public at large (Corazza et al., 2020). Conversely, sustainability reporting is seen by the agency theory as a system of checks and balances that help mitigate agency problems brought on by agents that often compromise environmental and social standards to achieve excellent financial results (Vitolla et al., 2020). Businesses exposed to a high level of social and environmental activity will surely find the sustainability component of their ESE to be compassionate. These businesses also have a greater obligation to disclose their social and environmental performance (Adams & Abhayawansa, 2022). This study adopted sustainability theory for the reasons mentioned above.

Financial performance and corporate Sustainability Reporting

Financial performance and corporate SR have a complicated correlation. One could argue that a company's expensive environmental activities and social activities programs deviate from their primary objective of increasing the wealth of shareholders (Ferrell, Liang, & Renneboog, 2015). Conversely, corporate sustainability can help reduce risk by shielding a company from the explicit costs that result from its reckless behaviour that affects society as a whole (Latridis, 2013). Furthermore, corporate sustainability activities can serve as a signal to outsiders about a firm's operations (Sweeney, & Coughlan, 2008; McWilliams, & Siegel 2000; Hu, Du, & Zhang, 2020; Emmanuel, Adenikinju, Doorasamy, Ayoola, Oladejo, Kwarbai, & Otekunrin, 2023). Specifically, corporate sustainability reporting—which is intimately tied to the performance of society, economics, and the environment as well as the proper application of reporting devices—is a crucial tool for long-term company prosperity for those who use financial reports (Bundy, Shropshire, & Buchholtz, 2013; Sen, Bhattacharya, & Korschun, 2006). Some research studies focus on the relationship between profitability and the level of environmental and social disclosure as well as the extent of disclosure of information regarding the environment with mixed results (Hu, Du, & Zhang, 2020; Cormier, Aerts, Ledoux, & Magnan, 2009; Dhaliwal, Li, Tsang, & Yang, 2011).

In GRI (2018), economic, social, and environmental topics are reviewed along with their significance in reporting on social impact, sustainability, dissemination of essential issues, nature and volume of essential issues, efficiency of risk management processes, identification and management of the economy and environment, annual compensation report, percentage increase in total compensation, and stakeholder involvement in the remuneration process. The studies on environmental performance are complexly analysed by other experts, and their findings indicate that enhancing environmental sustainability entails cutting pollution and implementing instruments in line with the global framework of environmental performance. GRI-based sustainability analysis helps to increase performance (Wood, 1991; Giroud, & Mueller, 2011).

Authors who examine the impact of social and environmental performance have found that there are beneficial effects on sustainability reporting initiatives (one way to measure this would be to look at data on emissions or the number of fines for environmental violations) (Clarkson et al. 2008). Businesses with strong social and environmental performance, according to Belal and Cooper (2011), use sustainability reporting to let their stakeholders know about it. On the other hand, companies that do poorly when it comes to social and environmental issues are hesitant to publish reports because they fear bad press. It is commonly known that by assisting in the identification of opportunities and risks that do not directly affect the company's finances, reporting on sustainability issues enables stakeholders to participate in corporate practice (Corporate Citizenship, 2012). Investors are increasingly looking to invest in companies that follow good sustainability practices because of the improvement in the long-term success of the reporting entity that comes from increased transparency, more effective decision-making, and the building and maintenance of confidence between industry and government environmental reporting (Burhan & Rahmanti, 2012).

Through sustainable reporting, negative effects related to social, environmental, and governance can be mitigated, enhancing and maintaining a firm's credibility and brand loyalty. It follows that the majority of those surveyed are employed by big firms that have a detrimental impact on the environment. (Intosai Wgea, 2013) In This instance, it serves as a vehicle for promoting a corporate image, demonstrating compliance, and showcasing the corporate point of view (Corporate Citizenship, 2012). a business that wants to survive needs information. Sustainability reports establish a repository of information (Corporate Citizenship, 2012). Enhancing management systems and the caliber of management information can be achieved through organizing and collecting information.

By concentrating on sustainability, one can promote creative thinking, develop new market offerings, and ensure sustainable, long-term growth, as mentioned by Intosai Wgea, (2013) and Uwuigbe, (2011). Sustainability reporting can also be used as a gauge for governance, to increase employee happiness, and to strengthen a company's capacity to hire new staff members (Aggarwal, 2013). Sustainability reporting forces a company to use recyclable resources, improve operational effectiveness, and make better use of natural resources. It might be a tool for saving money. (Saridewi & Koesrindartot, 2014; Uwuigbe, 2011). Reporting on sustainability offers a framework for measuring and establishing targets for firm objectives (Corporate Citizenship, 2012). It aids businesses in identifying opportunities, deficiencies, and completely novel objectives (Buniamin, Alrazi, Johari &

Abd-Rahman, 2011). Last but not least, sustainability reporting can help meet the demands for greater accountability and transparency brought on by the world's contemporary sustainability challenges and global financial crises (Intosai Wgea, 2013). In light of the foregoing review of the literature and its conclusions, the purpose of this study is to add to the body of knowledge regarding sustainability reporting in Nigeria by employing a subset of listed financial institutions. In particular, a few specific research questions are investigated in this research and null hypotheses are formulated and tested as follow:

H01: Reporting Economic activities 'does not significantly impact the ROA of quoted Nigerian financial services companies

H02: Reporting Environmental activities' does not significantly impact the ROA of quoted Nigerian financial services companies.

H03: Reporting Social activities' does not significantly impact the ROA of quoted Nigerian financial services companies.

3. Methodology

This study used longitudinal and ex-post facto research design. The extent of sustainability reporting in company annual reports and standalone reports is the independent variable based on the number of ESG activities involved by the company in line with the Global Reporting Initiative Guidelines G4 (GRIG4) index for Sustainability reporting. The reporting design of the Global Reporting Initiatives is used. The population is fifty-two (52) financial institutions on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (2021). A judgmental sampling technique was used to select a total of 30 firms as sample size based on the availability of their annual reports 2010-2020 in line with the study of Asogwa, Ofoegbu, & Odum, 2020). According to the Modern Sample Calculator designed by Raosifi Inc. which requires at least 50% of the population must be selected in line with Olusola, Shofolahan & Makinde (2014). The study used secondary data from the selected companies. Sustainability activities reporting data (independent variables) was obtained and used as the foundation for a content analysis technique. Using a multiple regression model, the data from the Sustainability Reporting Index was utilized to estimate the effect of corporate sustainability reporting on the performance of the selected companies. The data analysis process employed is Panel data analysis. This is because it incorporates both time series and cross-sectional data (Muriithi & Waweru, 2017). Environmental activities reporting (ENAR) include using energy, water, and emitting carbon dioxide Product and service stewardship, Waste disposal Compliance, and Biodiversity and infrastructure Compliance. Social Activities reporting (SAR) which includes; community involvement, anti-corruption behaviour, human rights, employee well-being and safety, Charitable donations, education, and learning, It's crucial to value diversity and equality. Economic (EAR) include market penetration, indirect economics, and economic performance, the impact of labour and industry relations, the supplier chain's value, management of risk. Size of firm – The entire asset worth of the business will be used as a control variable to determine the firm's size. The dependent variables employed as measures of company profitability were Return on Asset (ROA) in line with a previous study carried out by Asogwa Ofoegbu & Odum, 2020;

Laskar 2019; Emeka-Nwokeji & Osisioma 2019) on sustainability reporting and firm performance.

Model Specification

$$\text{ROA} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{EAR} + \beta_2 \text{ENAR} + \beta_3 \text{SAR} + \beta_4 \text{SOF} + \varepsilon$$

EAR = Economic Activities Reporting

ENAR = Environmental Activities Reporting

SAR = Social Activities Reporting

SOF= Size of firm

β = coefficient of the independent variable

e = Error Term.

4. Result and Findings

Regression Analysis

Table 4.1 displays the model summary of the data used in the study. The number of variations that the independent variable can explain is expressed as R squared. The Independent variable (EAR, SAR, and ENAR) can explain 20.2 percent of the variation, and the remaining 80.8 percent is explained by factors outside the model, according to the R squared value of 0.202

Table 4.1: Model Summary(b)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.420 ^a	.202	.190		.63795

Table 4.2 displays the F test has a value of 8.504 which is greater than 1 which means that it is good. The Significance value is at 0.000 which is less than 0.005 indicating that it is significant. This means that the Independent Variable can influence the Dependent Variable.

Table 4.2: Anova Table

Model	Sum Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	13.844	4	3.461	8.504	.000 ^b
Residual	121.279	298	.407		
Total	135.123	302			

(Source, SPSS 26)

a. Dependent Variable: ROA

b. Predictors: (Constant), SOF, ENAR, EAR, SAR

H01: Reporting Economic activities 'does not significantly impact the ROA of quoted Nigerian financial services companies

Table 4.3 presents the coefficient table of the Regression Analysis. The beta coefficient has a value of -0.053 which means that a unit increase in economic activity will lead to 0.053 decreases in ROA. This indicates that the EAR has a negative impact on ROA. The t statistic has a value of -3.099 with a significance value of 0.002 which is less than 0.05 which indicates that there is a significant negative relationship between Economic activity reporting and Financial Performance (ROA). Thus, the null hypothesis (H01) is rejected; that is Reporting Economic activities' does not significantly impact the ROA of quoted Nigerian financial services companies.

H02: Reporting Environmental activities' does not significantly impact the ROA of quoted Nigerian financial services companies.

The beta coefficient has a value of 0.035 which means that a unit increase in environmental activity will lead to an increase in ROA (Return on Assets) by 0.035. The t statistic has a value of 1.368 with a significance value of 0.172 which is greater than 0.05 which indicates that there is a positive but insignificant correlation between Environmental activity reporting and Financial Performance (ROA). Thus, the null hypothesis (H02) is accepted; that is, Reporting Environmental activities' does not significantly impact the ROA of quoted Nigerian financial services companies.

H03: Reporting Social activities' does not significantly impact the ROA of quoted Nigerian financial services companies.

Table 4.3 shows the coefficient table of the Regression Analysis. The beta coefficient has a value of 0.093 which means that a unit increase in social activity will lead to an increase in ROA (Return on Assets) by 0.093. The t statistic has a value of 2.931 with a significance value of 0.004 which is less than 0.05 which indicates that there is a significant positive relationship between Social activity reporting and Financial Performance (ROA). Thus, the null hypothesis (H03) is rejected; that is, Reporting Social activities' does not significantly impact the ROA of quoted Nigerian financial services companies

Table 4.3 displays the coefficient table. The beta coefficient has a value of -0.041 which means that a unit increase in SOF will lead to a decrease in ROA by -0.041. The t statistic has a value of -2.310 with a significance value of 0.022 which is lesser than 0.05 which indicates that there is a significant negative relationship between the Size of the Firm and Financial Performance (ROA).

The hypotheses were to test if reporting economic, social, and environmental activities significantly impacts the Return on asset (ROA) of listed financial institutions in Nigeria. From the Coefficient table of the Pooled Regression Analysis in Table 4.3 the p-values of EAR and SAR are 0.002 and 0.04 which indicates that there is a significant effect of economic and social activities' involvement on financial institutions' Returns on Asset while that of ENAR and SOF shows a negative impact of 0.17 and 0.022 on ROA financial institutions in Nigeria. This makes the alternative hypothesis of impact of ENAR on ROA of

financial institutions in Nigeria to be accepted thereby giving room for more research work on the study to be sure of the impact on ROA.

Table 4.3 Coefficients Table

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.368	.360		1.021	.308
EAR	-.053	.017	-.203	-3.099	.002
ENAR	.035	.026	.102	1.368	.172
SAR	.093	.032	.200	2.931	.004
SOF	-.041	.018	-.132	-2.310	.022

(Source, SPSS 26)

a. Dependent Variable: ROA

5. Discussion

The primary goal of this study is to explore the impact of corporate sustainability reporting on financial institution performance in Nigeria. Economic, environmental, and social activities were used as a proxy for sustainability reporting, while performance was measured using Return on Asset, as well as the firm's size as a control variable. The results show that there is a significant impact of reporting economic, and social activities on the Return on asset (ROA) of listed financial institutions in Nigeria while environmental activities have no significant relationship with the Return on asset (ROA) of listed financial institutions in Nigeria and thereby given room for more research work on the study of environmental activities reporting and ROA to be sure that of the impact on ROA. The finding is consistent with research conducted by Laskar and Maji (2016) and Hongming et al. (2020) on the corporate sustainability reporting and performance of Indian businesses, demonstrating the beneficial impact of specific sustainability metrics on financial performance. This finding backs up the signalling theory, which holds that businesses should reveal their excellent performance to set themselves apart from competitors who don't report on their corporate sustainability, lessen information asymmetry, improve their reputation, and sway the public's view (Mshelia, John, & Emmanuel, 2015). The finding also implies that some of the listed Nigerian financial services companies take into account the legitimacy theory, which postulates that businesses do not only view maximizing profits as their primary goal when conducting business but also give careful consideration to the surrounding environment and social activities.

6. Conclusion

This study aims to investigate the impact of sustainability reporting on financial institutions' financial performance in Nigeria. The result shows that there is a positive and significant impact of reporting economic activities on the financial performance (ROA) of listed financial institutions in Nigeria. The result also shows that there is a positive significant impact of reporting social activities on the financial performance (ROA) of listed

financial institutions in Nigeria. Nevertheless, there is no significant impact of reporting environmental activities on the ROA of listed financial institutions in Nigeria. This study concluded that sustainability reporting impacts the financial institutions' financial performance in Nigeria. This study shows that the GRI framework-based disclosure of non-economic information has a significant effect on corporate financial performance.

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Conflict Of Interest:

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